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Contribution of Education in Restoring National Identity: Example Tunisia: 1956 - 1987

Larby Foued (爱德)^{1*}, Liu Hong Wu (刘鸿武)²

¹ Institute of African Studies, Zhejiang Normal University

² Department of African Education and Social Development

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ABSTRACT

Several African countries have been subjected to colonialism, which has had a negative impact on their environment, economy, and society. Their independence has resulted in the nation-state building process approving self-determination in the accomplishment of state sovereignty and sustainable development.

The establishment of national identity is regarded as an important aspect of creating national unity, ensuring social stability, and long-term continuity of the state's mission. Many mechanisms, such as education, have played an important role in shaping and establishing this identity.

The Tunisian government has always prioritized education and sought to expand it and support it by investment as well as development and implementation of relevant plans to modernize it and improve its quality and profitability. Following independence, education became a state priority due to the importance of its role in forming national identity and future generations to continue the country's march of progress and advancement.

The Tunisian government has taken intentional and precise steps to reform the education sector at all levels. These reforms have included the education system, educational administration, personnel, curricula, as well as textbooks, and approved teaching pedagogies. In this context, we attempt to analyze the implemented measures in Tunisian education to rebuild national identity during Bourguiba's presidency term (1956-1987), following the country's independence in 1956.

Keywords

Nation-State Building, National Identity, Education, curricula, Tunisia, Arabize, Policies.

Introduction:

Since the pre-protectorate, Tunisian education has undergone several changes. At the time, Al-Zaytuna Islamic education was quite popular among the Arab Islamic world. To improve education, Hayeddine Pasha saw the necessity of reform. Therefore he established the “Sadiki College” in 1875 and included new disciplines in the curricula such as modern sciences, mathematics, foreign languages, and natural sciences. Simultaneously, Tunisia was facing political and economic weakness led to its gradual submission to French dominance. The French government took the required steps and signed the relevant treaties to protect its economic interests and impose its authority over the country.

Under French rule, Tunisia has experienced profound changes at all levels, including governance, administration, and in all the principal fields such as education. The progression of Tunisian education toward duality became stronger, particularly with the French presence. The French power used education as an instrument of influence and promoted French culture and language among Tunisians and foreign inhabitants.

In 1881, Tunisia has become a protectorate of France by a treaty of Bardo and it ended in 1956 with the declaration of independence, which is the result of resistance movements and political negotiations between representatives of the French government and Tunisian national movement components.

After its independence (1956), Tunisia has become a member state of the World Bank institutions and is eligible to receive funding from IDA. The World Bank’s first loan to Tunisia occurred in 1962 through IDA. The credit funded school construction in the Education Project for Tunisia and represented the Bank’s first credit for an education-related project. [1] Tunisian Government leaders have attached importance to the education system and relied on it to rebuild the country. The first president Bourguiba has implemented several policies complying with modernization and republican vision aiming to restore the national identity and make the citizen.

National Identity:

National identity has several social and psychological definitions. It resumed in person's identity and his sense of belonging to one nation or a state, [2] represented by a particular tradition, culture and language. [3]

On the other hand, in psychology is considered as an awareness of difference, a feeling and recognition of what is “we” and what “they” [4] [5]

Major Policies Shaping the Education in Tunisia:

To rebuild the nation-state, the Tunisian government has enacted various policies that have a direct impact on education. The state's vision was based on education as the primary vehicle for restoring national identity and creating citizenship. Tunisia has been a republican country since July 25, 1957, which is allowed to gain justice in the education field. The Tunisian approach complies with John Dewey's concept of how the educational system should be viewed as republican to ensure equity and fairness among society members. [6]

The country has also accomplished significant achievements in terms of policies and laws. As stated in the first article of the first chapter of the Tunisian constitution of 1956: "Tunisia is a free, independent and sovereign state: its religion is Islam, its language Arabic and its regime the republic".

The 1956's constitution has played an important role in defining the Tunisian identity, establishing a modern society, and ensuring citizens' rights. Tunisia's Republic is founded on the ideals of rule of law and pluralism, human dignity, solidarity, and development, as well as the right to personal development.

Several articles in the constitution stipulated the rights and the duties of the citizens and the government as well. The constitution's Preamble stated that the republican regime constitutes the most effective way of protecting the family and ensuring the citizens' right to work, health care, and education. Article five of the 1956's constitution states that "the Tunisian Republic guarantees basic freedoms and human rights in their universality, inclusiveness, complementarity, and interdependence." Article six stated that "all citizens have equal rights and responsibilities and are equal before the law." [7]

The constitution has strengthened the republican system and guaranteed the rights of citizens in work, health care, and education.

On August 13, 1956, the state has issued a "Personal Status Code" related to women's rights. It contains 213 articles, meticulously regulated laws regarding marriage, Spousal rights and obligations, Spousal disputes, filiation, dissolution of marriage, legal representation, and guardianship and Inheritance.

The Personal Status Code notably abolished polygamy, created a judicial procedure for divorce, and required marriage to be performed only in the event of the mutual consent of both parties. [8] The Personal Status Code aims to ensure the rights of women in education, work, and health care and their integration into society.

In 1958, the Tunisian government has issued "The Education Act" which indicates that the state provides education to all children starting at six years old (Chapter 2). In chapter three of the same act, the Tunisian government has approved free and compulsory education at all levels. Meanwhile, Chapter Seven stipulates that Primary education is unified and nationalized, and its essential goal is to empower the child with basic knowledge in the fields of language and arithmetic, aiming at emphasizing his capabilities, achieving compatibility between him and his environment, and revealing his talents that will guarantees guidance in the following stages of his learning. [9]

Education As identity Formation Mechanism:

The policies that have been implemented have paved the path for the establishment of a new educational system. The government has developed a reform to strengthen and modernize education.

Tunisian education underwent reform, becoming unified and nationalized. The new policies of the Education Act and the Personal Status Code have opened doors of education for all children of both genders, attracting the majority of Tunisians. The republican government issued these policies of free and compulsory education and women's rights, to educate the population, rally human resources and begin the state-nation building process.

Before the independence, Tunisian Education was under the influence of French domination, as the Arabic language was treated as a "foreign language". The content of education has no national reference that takes into account the development of the economic, social, cultural, and technical needs of the country.

During the protectorate, French curricula were implemented and the content was related to French culture. However, after the independence, the president has declared that the educational system should be based on nationalism and new subjects will be available regarding Tunisian history and geography. The new textbooks have created a national sentiment and summoned the history of resistance and national heroes, their sacrifices, loyalty, values, and glories in their fight against the colonial power. It's imparting knowledge, understanding, and instilling pride and patriotism in Tunisia's past and its ancestors' achievements. [10]

On the other hand, the Tunisian government has established an Office of Pedagogy (Diwan al-Tarbiya). This office assists in the development of unified curricula, the publication of a journal-keeping the instructor informed of problems and new developments in education, and so on. The office is in charge of supervising the creation and publication of appropriate textbooks.

The Office of Pedagogy has the mission of implementing new curricula by developing unified national Tunisian educational programs in History, Geography, Civic Education, Islamic Education, Arabic Literature, and Islamic Civilization, with a focus on the Maghreb countries (Morocco, Egypt, Libya, Algeria, and Mauritania). [12]

The new unified textbooks define the Tunisian identity in Arab, Maghreb, African and Islamic world and offer to the child the opportunity to discover his origins and understand his country's history.

Since 1958, educational programs have prioritized the teaching of the Arabic language. The Arabizing movement seeks to re-create the nation's identity.

As a result, by 1969, the primary education staff and system had become entirely Tunisian, and the ministry had released the French teachers and directors, changed programs and curricula, and established 22 regional inspection bureaus in 18 states to achieve the principle of decentralization. [13]

Between 1975 and 1987, the Primary Education Department has gradually Arabized education. In the third year of primary school, the scientific subjects were taught in Arabic. Furthermore, "Schools teacher's assignment" has evolved into a training center that incorporates Arabic into the teaching of mathematics, natural sciences, art education, civic education, handicrafts, history, geography, educational psychology, general pedagogy, art education, and physical education. Teachers earned a certificate that allows them to teach subjects in the Arabic language in primary school. In the years that followed, the school environment, correspondence, and Ministry of National Education documents were all arabized. [14]

The new educational system has seen remarkable development and growth. Primary education had 794 schools in 1957, with 5440 teachers on duty and 226.919 students enrolled. The implemented reform and the use of the Arabic language in the school environment, instruction, textbook, teaching method, and communication have significant benefits, restoring public trust in Tunisian education and allowing for the reconstitution of the nation's identity. By 1987, Tunisian primary education had 40.978 teachers dispensed in 3503 schools, with 1.319.372 students enrolled. Civic education had also played an important role in shaping the Tunisian identity. Tunisia has recognized its Islamic Arab affiliation, but to comply with the trends of the time, the country needed cultural openness and modern society.

The children of primary education have to study writing and reading, languages (Arabic as the first and French as the second language starting the third year), Mathematics (instruction in Arabic for the two first years, later in French), Morals and social values, Islamic education (Quran- From the first to the fifth primary year) and Civic History (fifth and sixth primary year), physical education, and environment and nature observation. [16]

The French language remains a language of instruction in secondary and tertiary education, specifically in scientific subjects and mathematics.

The civic, Islamic education has contributed to the child's understanding of modern society by acquiring and sharing republican values and building a civic culture based on morals, respect, and values of equity and dignity, as well as human rights. Furthermore, it strengthens his affiliation and patriotism.

Conclusion:

After the independence, the Tunisian government has made significant efforts in restoring the national identity and supporting cultural openness and modernization.

The constitution and the implemented policies in education and social life can be considered informal Civic education. They helped in maintaining order, promoting civic values, making the citizen, and organizing social life. On the other hand, through formal education, the government was able to recover the Tunisian

social aspect. The Arabization movement, the primacy of the Arabic language, new curricula, and national references all have a great influence on the Tunisian schools, national identity, and social-cultural perspective. The Tunisian schools tended to enlighten and liberate minds and create a rooted citizen of his culture, open to modernity, and become a contributor to his country's development. Education continues to play an important role in shaping and forming national identities.

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Authors name and details: Larby Foued, PhD Candidate, Institute of African Studies, Zhejiang Normal University. (IASZNU)

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